

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATED LESSONS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article provides an example of the importance benefits, and integrated lesson development of integrated lessons in primary education the course development was developed independently on the basis of the knowledge gained during the internship in order to widely apply it in the teaching process.

Key words: Integration, importance of integration, benefits and lesson development.

Nurturing a comprehensively mature and harmoniously developed person is one of the most pressing issues facing our society. There is a lot of talk today about organizing more integrated classes in the primary grades. Integrated lessons are effective in engaging elementary students in science and broadening their horizons.

Integration is a source of new evidence that confirms or deepens teachers observations and conclusions in a variety of subjects. They prevent students from getting tired and nervous by alternating different forms of activity. Integration is derived from the Latin word "integratio" –"restore", "replenish", "integer"- "whole". An elementary school student perceives the world as a whole. He is interested not in the name of the native language, reading, mathematics, the world around us, but in the variety of sounds, natural phenomena colors and sizes. One of the main tasks of a teacher is to show children that nature and everything in everyday life are interconnected. So can education integration meet today's demands? How to solve this problem? What is the role of the teacher in this process? Unless these issues are addressed, integration will not work. The main goal of integrating education is to lay the foundations for a good understanding of nature and society in the elementary school and to shape their relationship to their development that's why it's important for a small school student to look at an object or event from multiple angles. Throughout the integrated lessons, different lesson concepts are understandable to that age are identified. In this way, the topics are left in the memory of the students .Integrated lessons have a creative, unique transition methodology. In this process, the skill creativity and professionalism of the teacher are important in doing so, the teacher must first determine which lessons are suitable for integration and the similarity and logical connections between the content of the main topics of the different lessons.

Integrated lessons in the primary grades increase student's knowledge, as well as the formation analytical and generalization activities observed. The better the acquisition of new knowledge and concepts by primary school students, i.e., in increase in cognitive activity, the better their desire for education and upbringing will be compared to other periods. There for, the results of integrated lessons in primary school can give more results than ever before this means that science-related teaching in primary education develops students comprehension and thinking skills, encourages them to as quire in- depth knowledge, skills and competencies. The following is and example of an integrated lesson plan.

1 hour integrated open lesson development from a writing lesson for 1st graders

(Reading, the world around us, math)

Topic: The sound of the letter O.

Learning objective: To learn the sound of the letter o. Introduce students to the letter o. Learn to pronounce the sound o. Tk1 and Tk2

Educational goal: To educate students in the spirit of love for nature through acquaintance with the fruits grown in Uzbekistan. Teaching mother nature conservation. Tk5

Developmental objective: To increase students vocabulary and develop their independent work skills. Tk1, Tk2 and Tk5.

Course type: New educator.

Course methodology: Explanation, Q&A, ball and word find technologies.

Lesson equipment: Multimedia application, cross-section letters, a picture of a hunter on horseback, object beginning with the letter o.

Course:

1. Organizational part: The lesson begins. Greetings to the students. The duty officer will be heard. Attendance will be determined and students' readiness will be checked.

2. Reinforce the previous topic: Koptok technology can be used to reinforce the previous topic. Teacher turns to the class with the ball. An assignment on a topic covered in the writing class will be announced. The student holding the balls throws the ball to the other student, saying a word about the previous topic. The game goes on like this. The duration of the game is the time allotted by the teacher.

3. Description of the new topic: A copy of the pictures of the letter o in the textbook "Alphabet" is magnified on the screen. The sound of o is a vowel sound, and the air coming out of the lungs in the relatively long pronunciation of the o sound. Working with books and notebooks is important in explaining a new topic. Through topic conversations, students are introduced to the meaning of each , word and the educational aspects of the objects or thing depicted in each picture are incorporated. For example, the picture "Hunter" is used to explain to children about nature. Concepts relates to the pictures of the moon, soup, cherry, fire, hunter, squirrel and the pronunciation of the o sound in these words are discussed. When working with notebooks, children are reminded of the rules of writing.

4. Reinforce a new topic: Word Find technology can be used to reinforce students' knowledge of a new topic between a few words. The teacher is asked to identify words related today's topic. The assignment will take place at the time set by the teacher.

5. Summarizing and evaluating the lesson: The lesson is concluding. Students who actively participate in the class will be encouraged and evaluated.

6. Homework: Read and analyze the textbook at home. Find new words that start with the letter o.

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